

Methodology to investigate collection histories by studying collectors of specimens from Cayman Islands and Montserrat using GBIF and Wikidata

This methodology file describes an approach that (1) extracts collectors' names from GBIF, (2) disambiguates the name strings to Wikidata items and (3) analyses the data available on Wikidata using SPARQL queries, including the creation of maps and other graphics.

1) Extracting collectors' names from GBIF

Data of specimens collected from Montserrat and the Cayman Islands were extracted from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) in three separate downloads (GBIF.org, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c). Specimens were extracted with 'Basis of record': Material citation, Preserved specimen and Fossil specimen; 'Occurrence status': present; and 'Administrative area' (gadm.org): MSR (Montserrat), CYM (Cayman Islands), or a rectangular polygon that included all terrestrial parts of the two UKOTs and a substantial amount of the coastal waters. Deduplication resulted in 17,976 specimens and after removal of specimens with mismatching country codes 3,820 specimens from Montserrat and 14,087 from the Cayman Islands were included (Fig. S1).

Code

Extract all specimens and fossils from GBIF with the country code Montserrat

GBIF.org (31 December 2022) GBIF Occurrence Download
<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.r2cb8t>

```
{
  "type": "and",
  "predicates": [
    {
      "type": "in",
```

```
    "key": "BASIS_OF_RECORD",
    "values": [
      "MATERIAL_CITATION",
      "PRESERVED_SPECIMEN",
      "FOSSIL_SPECIMEN"
    ],
    "matchCase": false
  },
  {
    "type": "equals",
    "key": "GADM_GID",
    "value": "MSR",
    "matchCase": false
  },
  {
    "type": "equals",
    "key": "OCCURRENCE_STATUS",
    "value": "present",
    "matchCase": false
  }
]
}
```

Creates file 0234741-220831081235567.csv

```
$ wc -l 0234741-220831081235567.csv
```

```
3366 0234741-220831081235567.csv
```

Extract all specimens and fossils from GBIF with the country code Cayman Islands

GBIF.org (31 December 2022) GBIF Occurrence Download

<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.63cnbd>

```
$ wc -l 0234743-220831081235567.csv
```

```
9505 0234743-220831081235567.csv
```

Extract all specimens and fossils from GBIF with bounding boxes for Montserrat and Cayman Islands

GBIF.org (31 December 2022) GBIF Occurrence Download

```
{  
  "type": "and",  
  "predicates": [  
    {  
      "type": "in",  
      "key": "BASIS_OF_RECORD",  
      "values": [  
        "MATERIAL_CITATION",  
        "PRESERVED_SPECIMEN",  
        "FOSSIL_SPECIMEN"  
      ],  
      "matchCase": false  
    },  
    {  
      "type": "within",  
      "geometry": "POLYGON((-62.27426 16.64793,-62.10738 16.64793,-62.10738  
16.84337,-62.27426 16.84337,-62.27426 16.64793),POLYGON((-81.95466  
19.05858,-79.61622 19.05858,-79.61622 19.88397,-81.95466 19.88397,-81.95466  
19.05858))"  
    },  
    {
```

```
    "type": "equals",
    "key": "OCCURRENCE_STATUS",
    "value": "present",
    "matchCase": false
  }
]
}
```

Creates file 0234744-220831081235567.csv

```
$ wc -l 0234744-220831081235567.csv
```

```
3893 0234744-220831081235567.csv
```

Deduplicate the lists based on the GBIF ID

```
$ cat *.csv | awk -F"," '(!_[$1]++) > allCayman.tsv
```

```
$ cat *.csv | awk -F"," '(!_[$1]++) > allMontserrat.tsv
```

This way of using awk is quicker than sorting uniquely and it means the records stay in the same order

```
$ wc -l allMontserrat.tsv
```

```
3893 allMontserrat.tsv
```

```
$ wc -l allCayman.tsv
```

```
14089 allCayman.tsv
```


Fig. S1 Data filtering process for specimen records from Montserrat and the Cayman Islands, inspired by the PRISMA method. The process included the identification of initial datasets from GBIF.org, removal of duplicates, and screening for specimens with accurate country codes. The final dataset consisted of 3,820 records from Montserrat and 14,087 records from the Cayman Islands.

2) Disambiguating the name strings to Wikidata items

Each individual name string was disambiguated with the aim of linking it to a biographical entry in Wikidata (Wikidata.org). If a person could be identified and deemed sufficiently notable for inclusion in Wikidata but did not yet have an entry, a new Wikidata entry was created for them (e.g. [Q117485794](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q117485794)). Where biographical data, such as dates of birth and death, were available, this information was added to the corresponding Wikidata entity. Disambiguation followed the principles outlined in (Groom et al., 2022).

For the next step, each collector that had been identified uniquely to a Wikidata entry was unambiguously linked to their publications using the Wikimedia Toolforge Author Disambiguator tool (<https://author-disambiguator.toolforge.org/>) and to their specimens using Bionomia (<https://bionomia.net/>). A Bionomia public claims file was downloaded from <https://bionomia.net/downloads> on 28 December 2022 (Bionomia, 2024) and filtered to include only occurrences that matched the gbifID values from the Montserrat and Cayman Islands datasets. The filtered Bionomia attribution data contained 4,135 records. The relevant attributions from the Bionomia dataset were integrated into a PostgreSQL database that was created to store and manage the specimen occurrence data. The Cayman Islands dataset and the Montserrat dataset were also imported into the database. A table was created to store the disambiguated gbifID, recordedBy values, Wikidata identifiers and collection dates.

Code

Start from the Bionomia public claims file (Bionomia, 2024) and pull out the Bionomia attributions that have GBIF IDs that we are interested in.

```
$ grep -f allGbifIds.csv var/www/bionomia/public/data/bionomia-public-claims.csv | wc -l  
4135
```

```
$ grep -f allGbifIds.csv var/www/bionomia/public/data/bionomia-public-claims.csv >  
relevantBionomiaAttributions.csv
```

Create a postgresql database of all the specimens

```
COPY specimens  
FROM 'C:\cygwin64\home\quent\collectors\Cayman\allCayman.tsv'  
DELIMITER '    '  
CSV HEADER;
```

Some of the “countryCode” values are set to ZZ or others. I’ve set them all to either KY for Cayman

```
update specimens set "countryCode" = 'KY';
```

Add the Montserrat specimens to the table

```
COPY specimens
FROM 'C:\cygwin64\home\quent\collectors\Montserrat\allMontserrat.tsv'
DELIMITER ' '
CSV HEADER;
```

Parse the Bionomia GBIF record id to get rid of the URL so that it matches the gbifid in the specimens table

```
UPDATE "bionomiaAttributions" SET gbifid = split_part("gbifOccurrence", '/',
5)::BIGINT;
```

Match the people's names in my disambiguation spreadsheet with the names in recordedBy in the data from GBIF. Create a table with all the people with an orcid.

```
CREATE TABLE "myAttributions" AS
SELECT "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.orcid AS personid
FROM specimens, disambiguations
WHERE specimens."recordedBy" = disambiguations."recordedBy" AND
disambiguations.orcid IS NOT NULL
GROUP BY "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.orcid;
```

Add the wikidata ids to this table, as long as they don't have an orcid already.

```
INSERT INTO "myAttributions"
SELECT "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.wikidata AS personid
FROM specimens, disambiguations
WHERE specimens."recordedBy" = disambiguations."recordedBy" AND
disambiguations.wikidata IS NOT NULL AND disambiguations.orcid IS NULL
GROUP BY "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.wikidata;
```

Match the people's names in my disambiguation spreadsheet with the names in identifiedBy in the data from GBIF. Create a table with all the people with an orcid.

```
CREATE TABLE "myAttributionsIdentified" AS
SELECT "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.orcid AS personid
```

```

FROM specimens, disambiguations

WHERE specimens."identifiedBy" = disambiguations."recordedBy" AND
disambiguations.orcid IS NOT NULL

GROUP BY "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.orcid;

```

Add the wikidata ids to this table, as long as they don't have an orcid already.

```

INSERT INTO "myAttributionsIdentified"

SELECT "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.wikidata AS personid

FROM specimens, disambiguations

WHERE specimens."identifiedBy" = disambiguations."recordedBy" AND
disambiguations.wikidata IS NOT NULL AND disambiguations.orcid IS NULL

GROUP BY "gbifID", disambiguations."recordedBy", disambiguations.wikidata;

UPDATE "allAttributions" SET action = 'http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/iri/recordedBy';

```

Add all the identifications

```

INSERT INTO "allAttributions" SELECT "gbifID", "recordedBy", personid,
'http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/iri/identifiedBy' AS action from
"myAttributionsIdentified";

```

Add all the specimen attributions from Bionomia

```

INSERT INTO "allAttributions" SELECT "gbifid", personid, action FROM
"bionomiaAttributions";

```

Extract all the people with Wikidata IDs that have collected specimens

```

SELECT split_part("personid", '/', 5) FROM "allAttributions" WHERE action =
'http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/iri/recordedBy' AND personid LIKE '%wikidata%' GROUP By
"personid" ;

```

Add a spatial column to the specimens table

```

SELECT AddGeometryColumn ('specimens', 'geometry', 4326, 'POINT', 2);

```

Make a point from the longitude and latitude where possible

```
UPDATE specimens SET geometry = ST_MakePoint("decimalLongitude", "decimalLatitude")
WHERE "decimalLatitude" IS NOT NULL;
```

Find all the people on specimens that have not been disambiguated yet

```
SELECT "recordedBy"
FROM specimens
WHERE NOT EXISTS (
    SELECT -- SELECT list mostly irrelevant; can just be empty in Postgres
    FROM "allAttributions"
    WHERE "allAttributions"."gbifID" = specimens."gbifID"
) AND "recordedBy" IS NOT NULL GROUP BY "recordedBy";
```

```
SELECT "identifiedBy"
FROM specimens
WHERE NOT EXISTS (
    SELECT -- SELECT list mostly irrelevant; can just be empty in Postgres
    FROM "allAttributions"
    WHERE "allAttributions"."gbifID" = specimens."gbifID"
) AND "identifiedBy" IS NOT NULL GROUP BY "identifiedBy";
```

Extract recordedBy, recordedById, identifiedBy and identifiedBy from the dataset

Disambiguate each name string, that hasn't already got an ORCID or a Wikidata entry

If the person has a publication, but does not have an ORCID or a Wikidata entry then create a Wikidata item for them.

Use the toolforge author-disambiguator tool to link each person to their publications on Wikidata

```
SELECT specimens."gbifID", specimens."recordedBy", disambiguated2.wikidata FROM
specimens, disambiguated2

WHERE specimens."recordedBy" = disambiguated2."recordedBy" GROUP By
specimens."gbifID", specimens."recordedBy", disambiguated2.wikidata;
```

```
SELECT "gbifID", specimens."recordedBy", "disambiguated2".wikidata
FROM "disambiguated2", specimens
WHERE "disambiguated2"."recordedBy" = specimens."recordedBy";
```

```
INSERT INTO "allAttributions"

SELECT "gbifID", specimens."recordedBy", "disambiguated2".wikidata,
'http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/iri/recordedBy'

FROM "disambiguated2", specimens
WHERE "disambiguated2"."recordedBy" = specimens."recordedBy";
```

To check for duplicate rows

```
SELECT "gbifID", "recordedBy", personid, action
FROM "allAttributions"

GROUP BY "gbifID", "recordedBy", personid, action

HAVING COUNT("gbifID") =2;
```

Deleting duplicate rows

```
DELETE FROM "allAttributions"

WHERE id IN
```

```

(SELECT id
FROM
    (SELECT id,
        ROW_NUMBER() OVER( PARTITION BY "gbifID", "recordedBy", personid, action
        ORDER BY id ) AS row_num
    FROM "allAttributions" ) t
WHERE t.row_num > 1 );

```

As I only extracted the “Simple” CSV files from GBIF before I reran the queries above (see GBIF DOIs) and then extracted them as full Darwin Core Archives which I then stored in my Cygwin folder.

```

#Get all the wikidata IDs for specimens collected in Cayman

SELECT personid FROM "allAttributions", darwincore WHERE "allAttributions"."gbifID"
= darwincore."gbifID"

AND "countryCode" = 'KY'

AND personid like '%wikidata%' GROUP BY personid;

```

```

SELECT
    COUNT(DISTINCT specimens."gbifID") AS numberOfSpecimens
FROM "specimens"
INNER JOIN "allAttributions"
    ON specimens."gbifID" = "allAttributions"."gbifID"
INNER JOIN "caymancollectors"
    ON "allAttributions"."personid" = "caymancollectors"."collector";

```

For the Cayman Islands (N=110)

wd:Q104475270

wd:Q105330956
wd:Q1062746
wd:Q1063676
wd:Q108860143
wd:Q109309443
wd:Q109754544
wd:Q110189543
wd:Q110219600
wd:Q110471014
wd:Q110542875
wd:Q110543328
wd:Q110543724
wd:Q110543890
wd:Q110545364
wd:Q110548452
wd:Q110550642
wd:Q110551287
wd:Q110552706
wd:Q110552905
wd:Q110552938
wd:Q110553010
wd:Q110553070
wd:Q110558229
wd:Q110559376
wd:Q110559720
wd:Q110560886
wd:Q110561316
wd:Q110561450
wd:Q110566961
wd:Q110567400
wd:Q110905513
wd:Q110906132
wd:Q110906651
wd:Q110917965
wd:Q110941739
wd:Q110965547
wd:Q110965993
wd:Q111149326
wd:Q111152874
wd:Q112167932
wd:Q112622318
wd:Q112623519
wd:Q115206687
wd:Q117284520
wd:Q1242094
wd:Q13220399
wd:Q13521905
wd:Q1508177

wd:Q15429016
wd:Q1606467
wd:Q16091613
wd:Q1682880
wd:Q17579846
wd:Q18985139
wd:Q2063155
wd:Q20675576
wd:Q21062229
wd:Q21337578
wd:Q21339987
wd:Q21341721
wd:Q21387672
wd:Q21388002
wd:Q21389931
wd:Q21391610
wd:Q21392267
wd:Q21503065
wd:Q21611951
wd:Q22102514
wd:Q22102711
wd:Q22109087
wd:Q22112300
wd:Q22112473
wd:Q2585363
wd:Q26712883
wd:Q26738575
wd:Q28080402
wd:Q28945790
wd:Q2959465
wd:Q2982428
wd:Q30323412
wd:Q3568610
wd:Q39238335
wd:Q39238338
wd:Q446379
wd:Q49566535
wd:Q5407383
wd:Q54554038
wd:Q54803040
wd:Q54834110
wd:Q55038205
wd:Q5525851
wd:Q5646164
wd:Q5894487
wd:Q5959136
wd:Q6067165
wd:Q6167725

wd:Q6250065
wd:Q6286659
wd:Q64021484
wd:Q64629037
wd:Q7495121
wd:Q7794783
wd:Q8019050
wd:Q88091286
wd:Q89110041
wd:Q89707417
wd:Q91944752
wd:Q92184250
wd:Q97930448

For Montserrat (N=113)

wd:Q100537742
wd:Q105337589
wd:Q105635249
wd:Q106006901
wd:Q1066304
wd:Q106723777
wd:Q107416360
wd:Q108803291
wd:Q109309443
wd:Q109856372
wd:Q110189543
wd:Q110193829
wd:Q110198048
wd:Q110202162
wd:Q110487799
wd:Q110497349
wd:Q110526737
wd:Q110552706
wd:Q110567793
wd:Q110570855
wd:Q110571430
wd:Q110571934
wd:Q110901738
wd:Q110917514
wd:Q110917643
wd:Q110917774
wd:Q110938488
wd:Q110939985
wd:Q110941739
wd:Q110970212

wd:Q110970351
wd:Q110970441
wd:Q111517238
wd:Q111912734
wd:Q112168210
wd:Q112623415
wd:Q117485794
wd:Q122968
wd:Q12315588
wd:Q13220399
wd:Q1508177
wd:Q15480
wd:Q15892229
wd:Q1589882
wd:Q1960928
wd:Q20047235
wd:Q21339212
wd:Q21340568
wd:Q21341302
wd:Q21342059
wd:Q21388033
wd:Q21389202
wd:Q21389931
wd:Q21390055
wd:Q21390481
wd:Q21391578
wd:Q21395300
wd:Q21505447
wd:Q21607578
wd:Q22102395
wd:Q22107321
wd:Q22110023
wd:Q22111533
wd:Q22111730
wd:Q24196077
wd:Q26712297
wd:Q28860090
wd:Q29034918
wd:Q3098497
wd:Q33675708
wd:Q3420994
wd:Q353120
wd:Q383675
wd:Q4057357
wd:Q42325563
wd:Q4398741
wd:Q446379
wd:Q4775469

wd:Q4820667
wd:Q49566535
wd:Q50228600
wd:Q508940
wd:Q538252
wd:Q54834110
wd:Q55068282
wd:Q553714
wd:Q5646164
wd:Q5661696
wd:Q56690574
wd:Q56951108
wd:Q57192313
wd:Q5722285
wd:Q57556627
wd:Q60141841
wd:Q615605
wd:Q6232235
wd:Q6258846
wd:Q632088
wd:Q64053120
wd:Q64629037
wd:Q65055690
wd:Q7323572
wd:Q7325351
wd:Q7789322
wd:Q7961572
wd:Q87916990
wd:Q88832270
wd:Q89558205
wd:Q89558223
wd:Q91786528
wd:Q92039411
wd:Q94521073
wd:Q94535014

A comprehensive (dynamic) list with links to individual Wikidata records can be found here:
<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Special:WhatLinksHere/Q130465632>.

3) Analyses the data available on Wikidata using SPARQL queries

A. Creating a map in Wikidata of collectors' place of birth (P19), death (P20) and burial (P119), and employer (P108) - CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSERRAT - Query#1

```
#defaultView:Map

SELECT ?latlong1 ?latlong2 ?latlong3 ?latlong4 WHERE {

  # The Q-ids of the collectors collecting on the Cayman Islands

  VALUES ?collector {wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # Replace with your list of Q numbers
for collectors

  # print the label and preferred language

  ?collector rdfs:label ?collectorLabel .

  FILTER (lang(?collectorLabel)="en")

  # significant places for the collectors

  # place of birth (P19), death (P20) and burial (P119), and their employer (P108)

  OPTIONAL {?collector wdt:P19 ?pob .

    ?pob wdt:P625 ?latlong1 .}

  OPTIONAL {?collector wdt:P20 ?pod .

    ?pod wdt:P625 ?latlong2 .}

  OPTIONAL {?collector wdt:P119 ?pod .

    ?pod wdt:P625 ?latlong3 .}

  OPTIONAL {?collector wdt:P108 ?pod .

    ?pod wdt:P625 ?latlong4 .}

}
```


SPARQL query#1 results for Cayman Islands (upper panel) and Montserrat (lower panel)

B. Bubblechart of all subjects of papers written by people who collected on CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSEERRAT - Query#2

```
#defaultView:BubbleChart
```

```
SELECT ?subjectLabel (COUNT(?paper) AS ?paperCount) WHERE {
```

```

VALUES ?author {wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # Replace with your list of Q numbers for authors

?paper wdt:P50 ?author ;

      wdt:P921 ?subject .

SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}

GROUP BY ?subjectLabel

ORDER BY DESC(?paperCount)

LIMIT 20 # Adjust the limit as needed

```


SPARQL query#2 results for Cayman Islands (upper panel) and Montserrat (lower panel)

C. Bubblechart of all journals of papers written by people who collected on CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSERRAT - Query#3

```
#defaultView:BubbleChart

SELECT ?journalLabel (COUNT(?paper) AS ?paperCount) WHERE {

  VALUES ?author { wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # Replace with your list of Q numbers
  for authors

  ?paper wdt:P50 ?author ;

    wdt:P1433 ?journal . # P1433 is the "published in" property for the journal

  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }

}

GROUP BY ?journalLabel

ORDER BY DESC(?paperCount)

LIMIT 20 # Adjust the limit as needed
```


SPARQL query#3 results for Cayman Islands (upper panel) and Montserrat (lower panel)

D. List of all publications of people who collected on CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSERRAT - Query#4

```

SELECT DISTINCT * WHERE {
  # The qids of the collectors
  VALUES ?collector {wd:Qxxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxxx ...} # print the label and preferred language
  # print the label and preferred language
  ?collector rdfs:label ?collectorLabel .
  FILTER (lang(?collectorLabel)="en")

  # Get the scholarly articles for the collectors
  ?article wdt:P50 ?collector ;

```

```
wdt:P1476 ?title ;  
wdt:P577 ?date .  
}
```

Results SPARQL query#4: see CSV files:

- SPARQLquery4_Results-CaymanIslands
- SPARQLquery4_Results-Montserrat

E. Bubblechart of the occupations of people who collected on CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSERRAT - Query#5

```
#defaultView:BubbleChart
```

```
SELECT ?occupationLabel (COUNT(?collector) AS ?count)
```

```
WHERE
```

```
{
```

```
VALUES ?collector {wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # print the  
label and preferred language
```

```
?collector wdt:P106 ?occupation.
```

```
SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language  
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
```

```
}
```

```
GROUP BY ?occupationLabel
```



```

WHERE
{
  VALUES ?collector {wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # print the
label and preferred language

  ?collector wdt:P101 ?field. # P101 is "field of work"

  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}

GROUP BY ?fieldLabel

```


SPARQL query#6 results for Cayman Islands (upper panel) and Montserrat (lower panel)

G. Bubblechart of the memberships of people who collected on CAYMAN ISLANDS & MONTSERRAT - Query#7

```
#defaultView:BubbleChart
SELECT ?membershipLabel (COUNT(?collector) AS ?count)
WHERE
{
    VALUES ?collector {wd:Qxxxxxxxx wd:Qxxxxxxxx ...} # print the
label and preferred language

    ?collector wdt:P463 ?membership. # P463 is "member of"

    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
```

}

GROUP BY ?membershipLabel

Groom, Q., Bräuchler, C., Cubey, R., Dillen, M., Huybrechts, P., Kearney, N., Klazenga, N., Leachman, S., Paul, D. L., Rogers, H., Santos, J., Shorthouse, D., Vaughan, A., Von Mering, S., & Haston, E. (2022). The disambiguation of people names in biological collections. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, *10*, e86089.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.10.e86089>